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CONCEPT AND EVOLUTION OF MONEY SUPPLY SYSTEM TO MILITARY SERVANTS (CASE OF RUSSIA)

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Abstract: this article describes the concept and evolution of money supply of military personnel. In addition, the nature, principles, functions and structure of military allowances are analyzed. In addition, the evolution of the payment system for military personnel is covered in detail.

Key words: military serviceman, financial support, material support, evolution, material support, monetary allowance, military service, social support.

Military servicemen perform military service on the basis of a call-up or voluntarily - under a contract. Depending on how a soldier performs his military service, whether he is called up for military service or under a contract, the amount of monetary allowance, which is the main source of his support, depends on it. The topic of this dissertation - "Money allowances for military personnel: system, structure, development" - is relevant primarily because the need to improve the legal regulation of monetary benefits for military personnel has been emphasized by many scientists Slivkov A.S. , Prikhodchenko A.A. , Venediktov A.A. At the same time, the experience of recent years shows that all the changes made to the legislation on monetary benefits for military personnel, unfortunately, hardly improve the financial situation of military personnel and their family members, and secondly, monetary benefits provision of an element of the national defense and state security system should be aimed at creating appropriate conditions for military personnel to perform their duties; thirdly, provision of monetary allowances can and should encourage enlistment and conscientious performance of military service. their duties and long-term military personnel. Accordingly, the improvement of legal regulation should be aimed at strengthening the reproductive, stimulating and regulatory functions of money. The implementation of the state policy on the implementation of the rights and freedoms of military personnel, their social support, decent social status and standard of living, and the promotion of the prestige of the military service is defined in the "Strategy for the Social Development of the Armed Forces". "Main principles and directions for the development of the state military organization, which is the core of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation" for the period until 2020. The importance of monetary allowance is evidenced by the fact that, on the one hand, it is the main source of meeting the material and moral needs of military personnel and their family members, and on the other hand, it serves as the main source of meeting the material and moral needs of military personnel. . To encourage the work of military personnel due to the hardships and deprivation of military service, for example, the need to be in constant combat readiness, the ability to be called at any time to solve official tasks, including life-threatening combat tasks. health, relatively frequent change of place of residence compared to citizens, living with family members in remote areas and places with harsh or unfavorable climatic conditions, military servicemen undergoing military service separation from families and permanent residence, etc. Cash allowance is directly affected. happens in the

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armed forces. Such importance of the monetary allowance given to military personnel, its direct connection with the life and activity of the Armed Forces, their combat readiness, determines the introduction of changes to the legal documents in this regard, the continuous improvement and development of the legal regulation in this regard. . The socio-economic changes taking place in the Russian Federation, the development of free market relations and the implementation of the concept of transfer of allowances to cash determined the decisive role of monetary allowances in the system of material support of military personnel.

In scientific and legal literature, as well as in official statements of political and public figures, the current state of monetary allowance is assessed at a very low level that does not correspond to the nature and importance of the tasks performed by military personnel. At the same time, there is no single point of view in assessing the necessary and sufficient level of funds. At present, there have been few attempts to study the nature of monetary allowances for military personnel, organizational and legal guarantees, and the procedure for timely and complete delivery to each military personnel, as well as the powers of the state from a separate regulatory and legal point of view. bodies in the field of military service by citizens and military administration bodies, the right to fair remuneration for work in terms of consistency and efficiency. At the same time, all these issues require careful study and understanding. This applies especially to the issues of creating a new structure of payment for military servicemen, providing conditions for them to live a decent life, adequately covering all the difficulties and risks of military service, limiting their rights and freedoms. There is no doubt that it will be more effective if the work on increasing the salary of military personnel is carried out on a scientific basis. The object of research is the system of cash benefits for military personnel. The subject of research is financial and economic relations that determine the amount and structure of military allowances, the order of their delivery to recipients, as well as legal guarantees of timely and complete satisfaction with this type of assistance.

Achieving the goal includes solving the following tasks: • Studying the essence, content of the current legislation of the Russian Federation, the mechanism for determining the amount and procedure for paying military allowances to military personnel; • to study the history of the development of monetary allowances for military personnel from the tsarist army to the present state; • Review of powers of state bodies of the Russian Federation and military command and control bodies in the field of legal regulation of funds for military personnel and determination of conflicts; • to study the specific features of determining the amount of military payments in the context of socio-economic changes in society and military reforms; • analysis of the main trends in the development of legislation in the field of monetary benefits in modern times; • developing proposals for improving the legal regulation of military service pay; • developing proposals for improving the salary structure and level of military personnel.

The methodological basis of the research is the general scientific dialectical method of knowledge and scientific methods: historical, logical, sociological, systematic-structural, comparative legal, etc. General logical methods of knowledge (analysis, synthesis, generalization) are also used in the research. with their help, the existing legalities in the field of state-legal events, problems and ways to improve the legal regulation of monetary allowances for military personnel are identified. The legal basis of the research is the Constitution of the Russian Federation, the Budget Code of the Russian Federation, Federal Laws "On Defense", "On the Status of Military Servicemen", other federal laws, decrees and orders of the President of the Russian Federation.

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The Russian Federation, decisions of the Government of the Russian Federation, regulatory legal documents of the federal executive authorities, as well as orders of the Minister of Defense of the Russian Federation regulating the issue of monetary allowances to military personnel. The theoretical importance of the work is determined by the development of rules, conclusions and proposals that have a certain scientific novelty, including the determination of the nature of military servicemen's monetary allowances, the definition, determination and analysis of the legal mechanisms for the formation of its composition and amounts. Functions of the state bodies of the Russian Federation, military command and control bodies in this field in terms of their completeness, consistency and efficiency.

The nature, principles, functions and structure of monetary allowances for military personnel. Currently, a clear understanding of the monetary supply system for military personnel and its elements is not given, and their content has not been studied. Legal regulation of the procedure for determining the amount of benefits for military personnel needs research. "System" (from the Greek *Systema* - composed of parts, connected) is a set of elements that interact and communicate with each other and form a certain wholeness, unity. Analysis of current legislation and scientific literature allows to talk about the concept of monetary system in a narrow and broad sense. In a narrow sense, the salary system for military personnel is a set of principles, methods and methods for calculating, determining and changing the salary, allowances and other additional payments provided by law for military personnel. It should be taken into account that the established mechanism for the formation of monetary allowance and its delivery to specific military personnel is carried out through the entry into legal relations of the relevant subjects. The generality of this type of legal relationship, in turn, should be included in the system of monetary benefits. Therefore, in a broad sense, the salary system can be defined as a system of legal relations related to the determination and implementation of payment to military personnel in accordance with laws and other regulatory legal documents.

In legal and military literature, there is no uniform definition of the monetary allowance of military personnel. In determining the nature of money, the authors use different approaches and consider individual aspects of this social phenomenon. Thus, in the Military Encyclopedia, monetary allowance is defined as an integral part of financial support aimed at meeting the personal material needs of the troops, provided to them by the state in the form of regular payments of money, according to the official duties performed. On the other hand, financial support means a set of activities organized and carried out in order to timely and fully meet the needs of troops (forces) for funds, including financial planning and financing; request, receive, store, spend economically and appropriately, control their use, record and report. Thus, the important points in the given definition are, firstly, the funds are the financial support of the troops, that is, the activities of the competent authorities in the process of financing the costs of maintaining the troops, and secondly, in the definition, the purpose of funds, in particular: to meet the personal material needs of troops (military personnel). Starov B.F. and Kuznetsov N.I. In the textbook, the Military Administration indicates that monetary compensation is the payment of monetary rewards to military personnel for performing military service and military duties. In this case, the authors emphasize that in determining the salary of military personnel, it is directly related to the performed military service duties. The authors of the Legal Reference on the issue of cash benefits to military personnel are of the same opinion. Other authors, in determining the monetary allowance of military personnel, emphasize that it is an integral part of the material support of

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military personnel and, unlike natural types of pension, is aimed at meeting the monetary needs of military personnel. All the above points of view deserve the right to exist and do not contradict each other in any way.

They should be considered in a dialectical unity, which together reflects the important features of the concept of monetary allowance for military personnel. It should be noted that the concept of "monetary allowance" does not have a regulatory legal framework, unlike concepts such as "salary" and "salary", which are, for example, in Article 129 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation. Federation No. 197-FZ dated December 30, 2001. However, in Article 12 of the Federal Law of May 27, 1998 "On the Status of Military Servicemen". No. 76-ФЗ actually only reveals the salary structure for military personnel and names its main elements. At the same time, this issue is not only theoretical, but also practical. The lack of a clear and reasonable definition of monetary compensation significantly complicates the legal regulation of certain legal relations, because it creates controversial issues, for the resolution of which the parties (state authorities, military personnel) are forced to go to court. Moreover, even case law on some of these issues is not always consistent. Based on the analysis, it seems possible to determine the following main features of monetary allowances: - military servicemen's right to monetary allowances due to the specific nature of their activities and the duties assigned to the military organization to ensure the defense and security of the military organization. the country is established and guaranteed by the state; The exercise of the right of military personnel to receive pensions is carried out by transferring funds allocated for these purposes from the federal budget to their property; • monetary allowance is an integral part of all-round material provision (supply) of military personnel, aimed at meeting the material needs of military personnel for financial resources; • the term "monetary allowance" is used only in relation to military personnel, in relation to other categories of citizens "salary", "money bonus", "salary" and others; • the amount and order of payment of monetary allowances to military personnel are determined only by the state (state bodies and their officials within the scope of the powers granted to them by the current legal documents), they cannot be determined by agreement between the military personnel and the commander. (head) or other official; • the current legislation defines the content of the right of military servicemen to monetary allowances (amount, terms of payment, currency of payments) directly depending on the military position held, military rank, total period of military service, qualification level.

The nature and complexity of the tasks performed, the conditions and results of the service activity and some other conditions (cases of legal significance established in normative legal documents); It is related to the need to take into account all the features of military service related to the imposition of additional responsibilities on military personnel in relation to other citizens and the establishment of certain restrictions for them, as well as the need to establish financial incentives for military personnel without; for employees to conscientiously perform their duties, including in special circumstances, the current legislation includes a complex of compensation and incentive payments. It seems possible to give the following definition to this social phenomenon based on the identified characteristics of monetary allowance. Cash allowance for military servicemen is a monetary award determined and guaranteed by the state for fulfilling military service obligations, depending on the position held, the assigned military rank, the total length of military service, the nature and complexity of the tasks performed. conditions and results of service activities carried out at the expense of the federal budget, as well as social and compensation payments.

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The principles reflect the most important aspects of the organization and operation of the military payment system and, in their entirety, define the content of complex relations within this system. One of the main principles on which military servicemen's monetary allowance is based is to determine the amount of monetary allowance depending on the quantity and quality of military work of military personnel. The use of this principle in relations with military personnel allows the state to fully take into account the quantity and quality of military labor, specific types of their military activities. The main indicator that determines the amount of work performed by a soldier is the position he performs. The name of the position refers to the scope of the military serviceman's official activities, provides his practical experience, education necessary for the successful performance of his duties. This rule is taken into account when setting salaries for military positions: the more responsible the position, the higher the salary. The second principle of construction of monetary allowances for military servicemen is to take into account the characteristics of military service (the nature of military work, danger to life, age and service limitations, geographical and climatic conditions, danger to the life of military servicemen, age and service of military service determining the amount of allowance taking into account restrictions on military service. service mobility, military family budget formation resources). It is natural that the government of the Russian Federation takes into account all the specific conditions of this service when determining the salary for military personnel.

The third principle of the construction of monetary allowances for military personnel is the determination of the amount of monetary allowances for various categories of military personnel taking into account the order of service. Military personnel are divided into several groups according to the order of service: officers, guards, midshipmen, female military personnel, military personnel serving as private soldiers under contract, sergeants and conscripts. Just as the duration of compulsory military service for these groups is different, their level of satisfaction with livelihood is also different. If the term of service for a conscript is set to 1 year, military service for an officer is a lifelong profession. If conscripts are satisfied primarily with benefits, officers, bailiffs and contract servicemen have only a small part of their material and cultural needs covered by benefits, and the main part by monetary benefits.

Since the main responsibility for the combat readiness of military units rests with officers, the salary for officers is higher than for other categories of military personnel. The fourth principle is that the amount of monetary allowance should ensure the social importance of military service. A military career should not pay less than other civil service careers and a military career should not be less attractive than others. This principle of construction of salary system should ensure the following: a) payment for military work should not be lower than other professions in public service; b) the opportunity to receive free education in specialties that are in acute shortage along with military service at the same time; c) proportionality of monetary compensation (especially for young officers) with the content of colleagues in their specialty, employees of state and commercial organizations. The fifth principle is the universality, obligation and timeliness of payment of monetary benefits.

Cash allowance is paid for the military serviceman's time in service, treatment period, rest and holidays, the payment is made in the specified terms. The sixth principle of the construction of monetary allowance is the legality of determining the amount of monetary allowance in accordance with the Federal Law "On the Status of Military Servicemen", paying military servicemen in the amount that is undoubtedly due, strictly regulating the types of monetary

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allowances. These are the principles that are the basis of remuneration for the work of military personnel and are taken into account in the development of salary standards. The principles of military servicemen's pension must be considered as a whole, there is a connection and interdependence between them. It is impossible to make a correct conclusion about the salary of military personnel, taking into account only one principle, without taking into account others. Such a decision on monetary allowance does not allow to correctly describe the work of military personnel, to fully assess its quantity and quality, as well as the conditions of performance of military duties by military personnel. Military service has material and moral incentives. The principles of monetary construction cover only the scope of material order.

Cash allowance refers to material incentives and therefore only these incentives will be considered later. This, of course, does not reduce the importance of moral stimulation of military service in the ranks of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation. The government of the Russian Federation, when determining the salary level for military personnel, taking into account the principles of salary construction, also takes into account the economic capabilities of the state, because they set certain limits when determining salary standards. an important factor in solving the issues of introducing new types of wages. For example, proposals for the introduction of some new types of monetary benefits or the expansion of existing ones to other groups of military personnel are made, sometimes justified, but due to their absence, it is not possible to allocate appropriate funds for these purposes from the federal budget. Consequently, economics has a significant impact on the manifestation and application of principles.

Therefore, the principles of monetary benefits should be considered closely related to the state of the country's economy. In the system of market relations in the country, monetary allowance as a form of salary, as an assessment of the labor power of professional military personnel, is based on the performance of three main functions: 1) reproductive - monetary allowance should provide military personnel. while the volume of consumption of material goods and services is sufficient for the expanded reproduction of their labor force; 2) incentives - monetary compensation should ensure the resolution of labor incentive issues; 3) regulatory - financial aid acts as a regulator of the supply of military labor in the labor market.

The composition of the monetary allowance of military personnel is defined in Article 12 of the Federal Law of May 27, 1998 No. 76-FZ "On the Status of Military Personnel", according to which the monetary allowance of military personnel is established monthly. Salary according to the military post (hereinafter referred to as the salary for the military post) and monthly salary according to the given military rank (hereinafter referred to as the salary according to the military rank) employees (hereinafter referred to as wages), monthly and other additional payments (hereinafter referred to as additional payments in the text). The composition of monetary allowance is the internal composition of payments to military personnel established by the current legislation, which together make up the total amount of monetary allowance. When considering the composition of funds, the methods and rules for determining and determining the amount of monthly and additional payments must also be taken into account.

The concept of the structure of money is closely related to the concept of the monetary system. Their relationship can be defined as the relationship between general (system) and specific (structure). In this regard, the composition of monetary benefits for military personnel is a concept that describes the external expression of the operation of the entire system of monetary benefits for military personnel, and at the same time is an integral part of it. The composition of monetary

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allowances for military personnel under the contract is understood as the main method of grouping and classification of monetary allowances for military personnel depending on the characteristics describing the direction of payments, the frequency of their implementation and regulation by legislation. The Russian Federation, as well as the organic composition of monetary benefits as a share of individual payments to the total amount of monetary benefits. Let's take a closer look at each of these groups of monetary benefits.

Monthly salary includes salaries for military ranks and salaries for military positions of military personnel. This distribution of wages is the most suitable. It meets the specific characteristics of the military service, helps to improve the skills of military personnel, fully satisfy their personal needs in accordance with their service position, and encourages the activity and integrity of the service. The higher the position, the higher the salary for that position, the higher the military rank, the higher the salary for the military rank. Additional cash payments. In monetary allowances, in addition to monetary salaries, additional monetary allowances paid depending on specific conditions of military service, qualification, complexity of work and responsibilities of individual categories of military personnel are of great importance for different groups of military personnel. money wages are not taken into account. All additional cash funds are earmarked. Based on this feature, they can be divided into several groups: - promoting long-term service. Additional cash payments related to this group, such as percentage increases for length of service, etc., are intended for financial benefit of servicemen for the period of service in the army and navy, as well as in some units and units of the armed forces.

Armed Forces; - paid for special terms of service. The service of military personnel in military units, certain positions and a number of settlements is carried out under conditions that differ from the conditions of service in other military units, places and positions. Since these differences are significant, they are reflected in the form of a number of allowances and rewards about work, for example, percentage allowance for service in remote areas, allowance for special conditions of service, navy, etc.; - promotion of more qualified labor (advanced training). Special payments were established in order to improve the quality of work of military servicemen and increase their financial interest in improving their qualifications. Thus, military servicemen occupying positions with the same name, but whose work is highly qualified and of high quality, will be paid a monetary award for a class qualification (category of qualification), an allowance for a scientific title and a scientific degree; - paid for additional tasks.

Military servicemen are given additional payments if they are assigned additional tasks that are not related to the performance of official duties in their main positions or are related to the positions they perform, but are of a special nature and are not considered as part of their work. , for example, the official allowance of a cadet; - encouraging high achievements in professional activity. The purpose of additional payments to this group is to encourage personal achievements of servicemen, their impeccable service and discipline. Including: a one-time cash award for conscientious performance of military service duties, a cash award for completing military educational institutions, awards for personnel, including in aviation, for high quality of combat training and flights without disasters and accidents, and some others. others; According to the period of payment, additional payments of monetary allowance are divided into monthly and other (one-time) payments. Additional monthly cash allowances.

Additional monthly payments of cash benefits are such payments, the right to which occurs when certain conditions are established by law, and these conditions are valid for the entire period

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of validity. These include: · a percentage increase for seniority; coefficients (for military service in regional, high-mountain areas, for military service in desert and waterless areas); - Interest allowances for military service in the Far North, regions equivalent to it and other regions with unfavorable climatic and environmental conditions, including remote areas; -monthly allowances for scientific degree (scientific title), professor (associate professor) military positions; allowance for special service conditions; · service allowance for cadets; · monetary award for class qualifications (qualification category); · sea money; · bonus for service complexity, tension and special mode, etc.; · permanent increase of the monthly interest rate for military personnel who are allowed to state secrets; -cash prize for skydiving (landing with equipment); - monetary reward for diving activities, etc.

Other (one-time) additional payments of cash allowance. Other (one-time) additional payments of monetary benefits are payments for which the right is exercised, and in order to receive them the next time, the right to them must appear again, regardless of the previously exercised right. These include: · a one-time monetary award for conscientious performance of military service duties; · a one-time monetary award for continuous military service to officers whose service is related to parachute jumping; · a one-time monetary award for graduating from military educational institutions of vocational education; · monetary reward for long and continuous service on ships, ships and departments of their structures (associations); · a one-time allowance upon conclusion of the contract; · one-time allowance upon discharge from military service; Award for exemplary performance of military service; · material support; · other one-time payments. One of the groups of additional funds includes travel money.

Travel allowance. The travel fee includes: · daily allowance for a business trip; · cover the costs of booking and renting accommodation on business trips; Allowance for servicemen serving under the contract when moving to a new place of military service; · daily allowance for the route during the assignments and movement of military personnel; · field money; · reimbursement of travel expenses on business trips. The right of military personnel to receive monetary benefits. Military servicemen serving in the Armed Forces, if they: hold permanent positions in military units, ships, ships, headquarters, offices, institutions, military educational institutions, enterprises and organizations; study in military educational institutions; · there is. In some cases, military personnel may be sent to civilian ministries and agencies while remaining in military service. Such military servicemen are paid monetary allowances by relevant ministries and agencies in the amount and in the manner determined by the Government of the Russian Federation. Thus, we can say that monetary allowance is the main source of support for military personnel, which consists of monthly salary according to the military post and monthly salary according to the assigned military rank, which make up the monthly salary of military personnel, monthly and other additional fees.

In recent years, the modern Russian state and Russian society have significantly intensified efforts to restore the traditional high meaning of the concepts of "statesman", "sovereign man" in Russia. For this purpose, state regulatory measures are used in various spheres of public relations: state-legal, political, economic, informational, cultural, and others. At the moment, measures are being developed to increase the prestige of military service and strengthen military discipline in the troops. In the legislation of the Russian Federation, clarifications on the procedure of military service, improvement of the system of social guarantees for military personnel, etc. are ongoing.

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Historical experience in increasing Russia's influence in solving the most pressing issues of modern military development. and the appeal of military service is of particular interest. For the first time, "military manpower" measures were implemented in the middle of the 15th century. Warriors were always under the special attention and patronage of princely (state) authorities. For their conscientious service, they received plots of land that were leased to free peasants during military service. Provision of a detachment until the middle of the 16th century. it was done by collecting a certain tribute from the artisans and peasants of the city. It was created in the 50s of the 16th century. Streltsy troops armed themselves and underwent annual centralized training at the expense of the treasury. Military service exempted archers from the burden of taxation and protected them from the risk of becoming indentured servants or serfs. To compensate for the hardships and privations of military service, the state granted the archers the right to engage in crafts and trade, and also provided them with land. Since the 17th century. social guarantees for military personnel were significantly reduced.

The state did not want to fully pay for the standing army. It was either disbanded or reassembled during hostilities. Salaries are given only for participation in battles. This greatly reduced the combat effectiveness of the troops and led to the fact that the people serving were not interested in showing enthusiasm in military service. This process reflects the general weakening of state power, which, in turn, led to Polish-Swedish intervention. Peter's military reforms of the late 17th - early 18th centuries. was accompanied by regular improvements in wages and provisions, not only for officers, but also for enlisted men and sailors. Military expenses began to occupy the main part of state expenses (78.3% in 1701). The transformation of Russia into a naval power and the almost complete absence of professional military sailors forced Peter I, tempted by high wages and low food prices (6-8 times lower than European ones), to recruit foreigners who were ready for military service.

Service in Russia. At the same time, the salary of foreigners was 1.5-2 times higher than that of Russian officers. For example, the salary of a foreign naval officer with the rank of captain of the 2nd rank was 455 rubles per year, and the salary of a Russian captain was 300 rubles; foreign navigator received 156 rubles, Russian - 120 rubles, boat - 91 and 36 rubles. In November 1706, Peter I issued a decree "On the production of salaries for the ranks of the fleet", which increased the specified amount for each sailor according to his military rank, in addition to "salary cottages in all future years" . from the amount of monthly salary. In other words, the "thirteenth wage" was introduced. In 1716-1722, Peter I issued a number of national legal documents regulating the legal basis of the official activities of military personnel, systematizing and guaranteeing their social status. Significantly, new, higher standards for military and naval ranks were established by law. This applies primarily to cash payments and "provisions". At the same time, state-wide military personnel had to receive money first. The granting of another military rank, in particular, officer, allowed its owner to significantly improve his financial situation. For example, a lieutenant in the galley fleet received 11 times more than a midshipman; the salary of a second lieutenant was 7 times higher than that of a sergeant. Some of the money doubled. Such a serious difference in the material conditions of different categories of military personnel, of course, aroused their enthusiasm for service and the desire to constantly improve their professional training. In 1719, career creation was carried out only on the basis of competition (at least 2-3 candidates for a vacant position).

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When there was a disparity between the incomes and expenses of military personnel (for example, 1722), the introduction of the "Table of colors" served as a legal basis for determining the amount of monetary allowances and determining the amount of allowances given to officers. with increased prices and the cost of services) the Admiralty Council, and then the military department sent a special dispatch to the government, for example: "... due to lack of wages, naval and admiralty employees are experiencing great difficulties..". State thanks to the measures taken by the leadership, during Peter's reign even junior officers enjoyed a very enviable position in terms of financial support. was superior to most employees of civil offices, a social group that received

In 1930, the code of benefits for servicemen of the Red Army and their families and those forced into military service was revised. It envisages the granting of benefits to military personnel in the field of social insurance and maintenance, as well as maintaining the general and continuous length of service during the period of military service. The right to preserve the housing area and its priority provision, the establishment of a preferential payment for housing, as well as a number of benefits in the provision of medical care, sanatorium-resort treatment and recreation were granted. (preferential vouchers) to both military personnel and family members of command staff. In November 1932, military pay was significantly increased by the introduction of new official salaries. By the decision of the Council of People's Commissars on August 4, 1935, a percentage increase for seniority of 5 to 25% was introduced for commanders. In 1938, a higher regular salary for command and control personnel was again established, which made it possible to increase the salary of this category by 2.9 times. Thus, in the period from 1934 to 1939. salaries of platoon commanders increased by 2.4 times, regiment commanders by 3 times, and corps commanders by 3.64 times. In the Soviet Union since the 1940s. and prior to 1991, determining the amount of pay for military personnel was based on the application of the comparative method of military labor incentives. This method was developed by the Department of Labor and Social Affairs of the Ministry of Labor of the USSR. It was based on the need to differentiate wages for workers in different sectors of the national economy based on the characteristics of work in each sector. When using this method, the salary of equivalently qualified engineers and technicians working in the defense industry was used as a guide to determine the official salaries of military personnel. Accordingly, with the increase in wages in various sectors of the national economy, the official salaries of military personnel should have increased in the same proportion.

In the conditions of the planned economy, inflationary processes were weakly expressed in the period under consideration. Until the second half of the 1980s, the average salary of military personnel was higher than the national average.

Summary

In conclusion, we can say that money has a direct impact on the processes taking place in the Armed Forces. Such importance of monetary allowances given to military personnel, its direct connection with the life and activity of the Armed Forces, their combat training, determines the introduction of amendments to the relevant legislation, the continuous improvement and development of the legal regulation in this regard. The socio-economic changes taking place in the Russian Federation, the development of free market relations, the implementation of the concept of transferring cash allowances to cash determined the decisive role of cash allowances in the system of material support of military personnel.

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